

Distribution of Dielectric Relaxation Times and the Moment Problem*

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1 Abstract

A procedure for deconvolving time-dependent distribution functions from permittivity data is developed. The problem is reduced to solving an associated moment problem using a maximum-entropy procedure. The method is applied to synthetic permittivity modeling both for in-band and out-of-band regions. The numerical results indicate that the technique has potential for deconvolving the distribution function from the permittivity data.

2 Introduction

Estimation of the distribution function used in the distribution-of-relaxation-times model [1] (DRM) is important in interpreting relaxation mechanisms from permittivity and permeability measurements. It is possible to cast DRM into a moment problem so that the permittivity can be obtained from knowledge of the moments. In this paper we summarize our work on prediction of distribution functions from permittivity profiles. At this stage, the work is based on synthetic data.

The classical moment problem has been studied extensively over many years. The maximum entropy procedure is one way of performing the deconvolution in the moment problem. The method of maximum entropy assumes that there is an underlying probability distribution which describes the state of knowledge of a system [2]. Constraints are incorporated into the solution by undetermined Lagrange multipliers. Maximization of the entropy subject to constraints yields the probability density function.

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3 Permittivity Modeling

The distribution function $y(\tau)$ used in DRM can be used to define the real and imaginary parts of the permittivity

$$\epsilon' = \epsilon_\infty + [\epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty] \int_0^\infty \frac{y(\tau)}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} d\tau, \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon'' = [\epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty] \int_0^\infty \frac{\omega \tau y(\tau)}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} d\tau, \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_s and ϵ_∞ are the static and optical limit permittivities. Using a geometric series expansion for Eq. (1) and (2) we expand the permittivity in terms of moments

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon' - j\epsilon'' = & \\ \epsilon_\infty + [\epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty] \sum_{n=0,2,4,\dots}^\infty <\tau^n> \omega^n - & \\ j[\epsilon_s - \epsilon_\infty] \sum_{n=1,3,\dots}^\infty <\tau^n> \omega^n, & \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where the moments are defined as

$$<\tau^n> = \int_0^\infty \tau^n y(\tau) d\tau, \quad (4)$$

for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M$. Therefore the real part of the permittivity, being an even function, is expanded in terms of the even moments, and the odd part of the permittivity, being an odd function, is expanded in terms of the odd moments.

4 Numerical

The classical moment problem deals with the estimation of a probability density function $y(t)$ from knowledge of a finite number of moments (M) of a function.

Figure 1: The unnormalized distribution function, which is used in the example, as a function of relaxation time divided by a scale factor (rectangles) and the reproduced distribution (circles).

Figure 2: The relative complex permittivity as calculated by direct integration of the distribution function (rectangles) and the reproduced permittivity using a least-squares fit for obtaining the moments (circles). The extrapolation out-of-band is given by unshaded symbols.

The probability density can be found by the maximization of the entropy with the moments in (4) as constraints and is written as [2]

$$y(\tau) = \sum_{n=0}^M \exp(-\lambda_n \tau^n), \quad (5)$$

where λ_n are Lagrange multipliers.

The moments satisfy the following system of equations:

$$\sum_{n=1}^M n \langle \tau^{i+n-2} \rangle = \lambda_n = (i-1) \langle \tau^{i-2} \rangle + a^{i-1} y(a) - b^{i-1} y(b), \quad (6)$$

for $i=1, 2, \dots, M$. Equation (6) will be used to find the Lagrange multipliers and therefore the distribution function from the moments.

As an application a distribution function is constructed from Eq. (5) for the case where 4 Lagrange multipliers are given. This distribution, which is representative of liquids, is shown in Fig. 1. The distribution function is then used to form the permittivity by use of Eqs. (1) and (2). Next the moments are calculated from this permittivity distribution by a least-squares fit and by comparison to Eq. (3). Then using these moments, we determine the Lagrange multipliers and consequently the reconstructed distribution function and permittivity shown in Figs. 1 and 2. We see that reasonable reproduction can be reached from calculated moments. Extrapolation of the permittivity out of the given band is also possible.

5 Conclusions

The calculation of the permittivity in DRM can be reduced to a moment problem. The moment problem, treated by maximum-entropy methods, can be reduced to a set of nonlinear equations. The related distribution function can be effectively modeled by the approach developed in this paper. The permittivity can also be extrapolated to out-of-band regions using the calculated impulse response function. The limitations are currently being studied.

References

- [1] C. J. F. Bottcher and P. Bordewijk, *Theory of Electric Polarization*. Vol. I and II, New York: Elsevier, 1978.
- [2] E. Jaynes, "Information theory and statistical mechanics," *Phys. Rev.*, vol. 106, p. 620, 1957.